

B-WaterSmart Data Management Plan

Deliverable 8.3
(final version M48)

B-WaterSmart - Data Management Plan

Deliverable 8.3

Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) shows which data has been generated and collected, and how these data sets were used, exploited, made accessible, stored, and preserved within the B-WaterSmart project. This report is the final version of the DMP, prepared at the end of the project.

The document was prepared in compliance with the EC guideline on data management in H2020, supervised by the independent Ethics advisor of the project. It describes the data management approach for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by B-WaterSmart and includes information on:

- I. the handling of research data during and after the end of the project;
- II. what data will be collected, processed and/or generated;
- III. which methodology and standards will be applied;
- IV. whether data will be shared/made open access; and
- V. how data will be curated and preserved.

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Dissemination level

- PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
Please specify: _____
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ALLEA	All European Academies
ARCO rights	Right of access, rectification, cancellation, and opposition
BDGS	Bundesdatenschutzgesetz
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable
FLOSS	Free, libre and open source software
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISA	International Sociological Association
M	Month
MS	Milestone
S2O	Subscribe-to-Open
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

A new element in the Horizon 2020 is the use of data management plans detailing what data the projects generate and how this data are made accessible. The purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that was used by the B-WaterSmart project with regard to all the datasets that were generated or collected by the project. This deliverable presents the final version of the DMP for the B-WaterSmart project. It presents the key considerations made to ensure open access to the project's publications and describes the background for why and how B-WaterSmart needs to be an open access project. Furthermore, this deliverable describes the data sets that were gathered, processed and analysed. These data set descriptions follow the DMP template provided by the European Commission. This template was circulated to the work packages responsible of the project, in order to compile the WP specific plans for gathering and analysis of data as well as the methods and processes to be applied to ensure compliance with ethics requirements. In cases in which open access to research data represents a risk for compromising the privacy of participants, data will not be shared or made accessible. The DMP is not a fixed document, but evolved during the lifespan of the project.

By month 48, a final assessment of the produced datasets was made, in which all datasets were assessed regarding their confidentiality, usefulness, and reusability. The results of this assessment led to the decision that only one dataset was made publicly available via open data repositories. There are also four open sources codes that the B-WaterSmart Project published in open data repositories. For all other data sets, it was assessed that due to confidentiality, usefulness or reusability issues, the data sets were not published separately but as part of the digital tool that they were collected for. The tool links and the persons that can be contacted in order to get access to the tools and test data sets were included in the final and public versions of D3.4 and D3.5. Besides, all public deliverables accepted by M48, were also uploaded to Zenodo, to ensure their availability after the closing of the B-WaterSmart deadline.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of this document

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data management life cycle for the data sets collected and processed by B-WaterSmart. The DMP outlines the handling of research data during the project, and how and what parts of the data sets will be made available after the project has been completed. This includes an assessment of when and how data can be shared without disclosing directly or indirectly identifiable information from partners involved in the project and its living labs.

In principle, publicly funded research data are a public good, produced for the public interest that should be made openly available with as few restrictions as possible in a timely and responsible manner that does not harm intellectual property and confidentiality. On this basis, the DMP intends to help researchers consider at an early stage, when research is being designed and planned, how data will be managed during the research process and shared afterwards with the wider research community.

The DMP specifies the availability of research data, describes measures to ensure data are properly stored, handled, and anonymized to ensure the privacy of informants and respondents, and to ensure the open data strategy does not violate the terms on ethical procedures and personal data made with the Communities of Practice of each living lab operated by WP1 (see MS3 chapter 3.4). In any case, the developed technologies (WP2), tools and models within the project (WP3) do not contain any case or company specific information, sensitive data (personal data, customer information), or related inputs and as such, its availability is no threat to any technology or data service provider, water utility or industrial partner as well as any other party involved in the living labs.

Regarding access to research data, B-WaterSmart tried to make the data and metadata available as much as possible. Project members have access to both data and metadata on the internal project data base on Nextcloud. Research data that was considered non-sensitive, useful, reusable has been archived at the open access European repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) to ensure re-use of public data in future research projects and follow-up studies.

Regarding open access to scientific publications, B-WaterSmart aimed to publish in open access journals (gold open access), and to establish links to publications behind pay-walls available as final peer-reviewed manuscripts in an online repository after publication (green open access). To ensure gold open access, the B-WaterSmart project placed priority on relevant journals choosing gold open access journals. Special focus of the project's dissemination activities was given to the new Open Research Europe portal and the open access initiative by IWA Publishing. Following the recommendations of the data management plan ensured that partners only submitted their work to journals with easy access to third parties.

The benefits of a well-designed DMP not only concern the way data is treated but also the successful outcome of the project itself. A properly planned DMP guides the researchers first to think about what to do with the data and then how to collect, store and process them, etc. Furthermore, planning in data treatment is important for addressing timely security, privacy, and ethical aspects. This way the research data is kept on track in cases of possible staff or other changes. The DMP can also increase preparedness for possible data requests. In short, planned activities, such as implementation of well-designed DMP, stand a better chance of meeting their goals than unplanned ones.

1.2. Intended readership

This deliverable is public. However, the intended readership is mainly the B-WaterSmart project team since the DMP provides guidance on data management relevant for all project partners and participants. It is particularly relevant for partners responsible for smart data solutions (WP3), technical solution (WP2) and dissemination (WP7).

This process of planning is also a process of communication, increasingly important in a multi-partner research. The characteristics of collaboration should be accordingly harmonized among project partners from different organizations or different countries. The DMP also provides an ideal opportunity to engender best practice with regards to e.g., file formats, metadata standards, storage, and risk management practices, leading to greater longevity and sustainability of data and higher quality standards. Ultimately, the DMP should engage researchers in conversations with those providing the services. In this context, the DMP should become a document in accordance with relevant standards and community best practice.

1.3. Structure of this document

The deliverable is structured in accordance with the recommendations on structure provided in the H2020 Data Management Plan template:

- Section 1 is the introductory chapter describing the main purposes of the DMP.
- Section 2 describes the guiding principles for the overall data management of B-WaterSmart.
- Section 3 presents the information available on data sets gathered, processed, and analysed within the project and describes measures implemented to fulfill the FAIR data principles.
- Section 4 is dedicated to information on allocation of resources and costs for FAIR data management in this project.
- Section 5 focusses on procedures implemented to ensure data security (including rules for data transfer between European countries and non-European countries).
- Section 6 is dedicated to ethical aspects in relation to the handling of personal data in B-WaterSmart.

1.4. Relationship with other deliverables

This document complements the following deliverables:

- D1.1 - CoPs architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL
- D5.1 - Manual on stakeholder mapping and engagement
- D3.1 - B-WaterSmart FIWARE based interoperability framework
- D7.1 - B-WaterSmart Knowledge portal upgrades
- D7.5/D7.6 - Dissemination & communication strategy & plan
- D7.7/D7.8 - Exploitation and business plan for B-WaterSmart solutions
- D7.9 - Specific exploitation concepts for key B-WaterSmart solutions
- D8.2. Quality Assurance Plan

2. Code of Conduct

One of the most important aspects regarding data management is the need to define which possible uses are allowed on the data pool built from the project. The data usage can be managed by defining specific purposes, establishing ethical guidelines, or generating a general Codes of Conduct. The B-WaterSmart Code of Conduct was created based on the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2017), the Code of Ethics published by the International Sociological Association (ISA, 2021), and the Data Science Code of Professional Conduct established by the Data Science Association (Data Science Association, 2021). It is tailored to the use within the whole project, covering all cases and data sources that will be used across all living labs, paying special attention to data science approaches in the project. The following chapters describe the terminology and the rules that the B-WaterSmart Code of Conduct is based on:

2.1. Terminology

Table 1: Terminology used in Code of Conduct

Terminus	Meaning
Agency Problem	a conflict of interest that may arise in any relationship where one party is expected to act in another's best interests (e.g., living lab mentor providing information on behalf of the LL owner, LL owner/mentor providing information on behalf of the LL/CoP partners). The two parties have different interests and asymmetric information, such that the principal cannot directly ensure that the agent is always acting in its (the principal's) best interests. At the same time moral hazard may arise when there is a lack of incentive to guard against risk where one is protected from its consequences. Both may also affect politicians and academics
Algorithm	a process or set of rules to be followed in calculations or other problem-solving operations to achieve a goal, especially a mathematical rule or procedure used to compute a desired result, produce the answer to a question or the solution to a problem in a finite number of steps
Causation	the relationship between cause and effect backed by scientific evidence (e.g., relationship between an event (the cause) and a second event (the effect), where the second event is understood because of the first)
Cherry picking	pointing to individual cases or data that seem to confirm a particular position, while ignoring a significant portion of related cases or data that may contradict that position and may constitute scientific fraud, suppressing evidence, or the fallacy of incomplete evidence
Confidential Information	information that you create, develop, receive, use, or learn during your tasks within project that is not generally known by the public about the participants or participating organizations of the project and that should not be made public without the participant´ or participating organization´ s allowance
Correlation	any of a broad class of statistical relationships involving dependence

Data	a tangible or electronic record of raw (factual or non-factual) information (as measurements, statistics or information in numerical form that can be digitally transmitted or processed) used as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation and must be processed or analyzed to be meaningful
Data Mining	using sophisticated data search capabilities and statistical algorithms to discover patterns and correlations in data sets to discover new meaning in data
Data Quality	rating the veracity of data
Data Science	the scientific study of the creation, validation, and transformation of data to create meaning
Fraud or fraudulent	denotes conduct that is deceitful in the sense of falsification (making up results and recording them as if they were real), fabrication (manipulating research materials, equipment or processes or changing, omitting or suppressing data or results without justification), plagiarism (using other people's work and ideas without giving proper credit to the original source, thus violating the rights of the original author(s) to their intellectual outputs) or with regards to the substantive or procedural law of the applicable jurisdiction
Knowingly, known, or knows	denotes actual knowledge of the fact in question. A person's knowledge may be inferred from circumstances
Knowledge	information backed by scientific evidence that creates meaning
Machine Learning	the field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed
Protagoras Problem	engaging in consequentially distorting assumptions "ifs" and calling it "science" and "evidence". The key is sincerity in assumptions
Reasonable or reasonably	when used in relation to conduct by a researcher denotes the conduct of a reasonably prudent and competent researcher
Spurious Correlation	a correlation between two variables that does not result from any direct relation between them but from their relation to other variables
Statistically Significant	a statistical assessment of whether observations reflect a pattern rather than just chance and may or may not be meaningful
Statistics	the practice or science of collecting and analyzing numerical data in large quantities
Substantial	when used in reference to degree or extent means a material matter of clear and weighty importance
Variable	a value that may change within the scope of a given problem or set of operations and may be independent or dependent

2.2. Rules

The research in B-WaterSmart should follow the good research practices in the fields of research environment, training, supervision and mentoring, research procedures, safeguards, data practices and management, collaborative working, publication, and dissemination as well as reviewing, evaluating, and editing defined by European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. These good research practices are based on four fundamental principles of research integrity (ALLEA, 2017):

- A.** Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis, and the use of resources.
- B.** Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way.
- C.** Respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.
- D.** Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organization, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

With regards to data practices and management this means that all researchers, research institutions and organizations of B-WaterSmart:

- 1.** ensure appropriate stewardship and curation of all data and research materials, including unpublished ones, with secure preservation for a reasonable period.
- 2.** ensure access to data is as open as possible, as closed as necessary, and where appropriate in line with the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) for data management.
- 3.** provide transparency about how to access or make use of their data and research materials.
- 4.** acknowledge data as legitimate and citable products of research.
- 5.** ensure that any contracts or agreements relating to research outputs include equitable and fair provision for the management of their use, ownership, and/or their protection under intellectual property rights.

Furthermore, data science approaches within B-WaterSmart should follow these common rules (based on Data Science Association, 2021):

- 6.** Competent data science research requires the knowledge, skill, thoroughness, and preparation reasonably necessary for the tasks.
- 7.** B-WaterSmart partners shall not engage or assist in collecting, processing, or transferring data that they know is criminal or fraudulent.
- 8.** Research results based on data sets need to be explained to an extent reasonably necessary to provide others a transparent and understandable knowledge basis to make informed decisions.

9. All information that is created, developed, received, used, or learned during the project, and that is not generally known by the public, is confidential. The researcher has a duty to protect all confidential information, regardless of its form or format, from the time of its creation or receipt until its authorized disposal. Confidential information is an asset. Protecting this information is critical to ensure compliance with laws and regulations as well as the ethical requirements of good research practice and to build trust.
10. Researchers may reveal information relating to the extent the researcher reasonably believes necessary to prevent project partners from committing a crime or fraud that is reasonably certain to result in substantial injury to the financial interests or property of another.
11. Researchers must ensure to prevent the inadvertent or unauthorized disclosure of, or unauthorized access to, information, which means:
 - a. Not displaying, reviewing, or discussing confidential information in public places, in the presence of third parties or that may be overheard;
 - b. Not e-mailing confidential information outside of the organization or professional practice to a personal e-mail account or otherwise removing confidential information by removing hard copies or copying it to any form of recordable digital media device; and
 - c. Communicating confidential information to anybody who is not necessarily involved in this task.
12. Researchers shall comply with the procedures and rules defined in the Grant Agreement that apply to the acceptance, proper use, and handling of confidential information, as well as any additional written agreements relating to confidential information.
13. Researchers shall protect confidential information after termination of work for the partner that provided the information.
14. A researcher shall return any and all confidential information in possession or control upon termination of the project.
15. Data sets shall be rated regarding quality of data. This rating shall be disclosed to enable informed decision-making. Bad or uncertain data quality may communicate a false reality or promote an illusion of understanding. The researcher shall take reasonable measures to protect the data user from relying and making decisions based on bad or uncertain data quality.
16. Data sets shall be rated regarding the quality of evidence. This rating shall be disclosed to enable informed decision-making. The researcher understands that evidence may be weak or strong or uncertain and shall take reasonable measures to protect the data user from relying and making decisions based on weak or uncertain evidence.
17. If a researcher believes a project partner is misusing research results to communicate a false reality or promote an illusion of understanding, the researcher shall take reasonable remedial measures, including disclosure to the project partner. The researcher shall take reasonable measures to encourage the project partner to use data science appropriately, including, if necessary, disclosure to the project leader.

18. If a researcher knows that a project partner intends to engage, is engaging or has engaged in criminal or fraudulent conduct related to the research provided, the researcher shall take reasonable remedial measures, including, if necessary, disclosure to the project leader.

19. A researcher shall not knowingly:

- a. fail to use scientific methods in performing data science;
- b. fail to rank the quality of evidence in a reasonable and understandable manner;
- c. claim weak or uncertain evidence is strong evidence;
- d. misuse weak or uncertain evidence to communicate a false reality or promote an illusion of understanding;
- e. fail to rank the quality of data in a reasonable and understandable manner;
- f. claim bad or uncertain data quality is good data quality;
- g. misuse bad or uncertain data quality to communicate a false reality or promote an illusion of understanding;
- h. fail to disclose any and all data science results or engage in cherry-picking;
- i. fail to attempt to replicate data science results;
- j. fail to disclose that data science results could not be replicated;
- k. misuse data science results to communicate a false reality or promote an illusion of understanding;
- l. fail to disclose failed experiments or disconfirming evidence known researcher to be directly adverse to the position of the researcher;
- m. offer evidence that the researcher knows to be false. If a researcher questions the quality of data or evidence the researcher must disclose this information. If a researcher has offered material evidence and the researcher comes to know of its falsity, the researcher shall take reasonable remedial measures, including disclosure to the recipients of his research results. A researcher may disclose and label evidence the researcher reasonably believes is false;
- n. cherry-pick data and data science evidence.

20. A researcher shall use reasonable diligence when designing, creating, and implementing algorithms to avoid harm. The researcher shall disclose any real, perceived, or hidden risks from using the algorithm. After full disclosure, user is responsible for making the decision to use or not use the algorithm. If a researcher reasonably believes an algorithm will cause harm, the researcher shall take reasonable remedial measures. The researcher shall take reasonable measures to encourage the user to use the algorithm appropriately.

- 21.** A researcher shall use reasonable diligence when designing, creating, and implementing machine learning systems to avoid harm. The researcher shall disclose to the recipient of his research results any real, perceived, or hidden risks from using a machine learning system. After full disclosure, the user is responsible for making the decision to use or not use the machine learning system. If a researcher reasonably believes the machine learning system will cause harm, the researcher shall take reasonable remedial measures. The researcher shall take reasonable measures to encourage the user to use the machine learning system appropriately.
- 22.** A researcher shall use its reasonable best efforts to assign value and meaning to the following concepts when conducting data science:

 - a. "Statistically Significant"
 - b. "Correlation"
 - c. "Spurious Correlation"
 - d. "Causation"
- 23.** A researcher shall not engage in "Cherry picking" (pointing to individual cases or data that seem to confirm a particular position, while ignoring a significant portion of related cases or data that may contradict that position) when conducting data science. The researcher understands that engaging in "Cherry picking" may constitute scientific fraud, suppressing evidence, or the fallacy of incomplete evidence.
- 24.** A researcher shall not present incomplete evidence as real data science evidence. A researcher may present a theory constituting incomplete evidence but shall label and clearly communicate the use of incomplete evidence.
- 25.** A researcher shall use its reasonable best efforts to question assumptions and avoid engaging in consequentially distorting assumptions "if's" and calling it "science" and "evidence" (also known as the "Protagoras Problem").
- 26.** A researcher shall use its reasonable best efforts to recognize "agency problems" when conducting data science. The researcher needs to disclose all conflicts of interest in any case. In case of a conflict of interest, the researcher shall inform the project coordinator and the project partner(s) potentially affected by the conflict of interest, to develop an adequate solution acceptable to all parties involved.
- 27.** A researcher shall use reasonable diligence to detect, recognize, disclose, and factor real, perceived and potentially hidden risks in using data science. The prudent researcher understands that data creators and the designers and builders of data management systems have more knowledge than the researcher and can hide risks in the foundations and interpretations / bias of the raw, created and manipulated data. The researcher shall take reasonable remedial measures, including disclosure of risks to the recipient of his research results.
- 28.** A researcher shall use the data science method which consists of the following steps:

- a. Careful observations of data, data sets and relationships between data;
- b. Deduction of meaning from the data and different data relationships;
- c. Formation of hypotheses;
- d. Experimental or observational testing of the validity of the hypotheses. To be termed scientific, a method of inquiry must be based on empirical and measurable evidence subject to specific principles of reasoning.

3. B-WaterSmart measures to ensure FAIR data management

B-WaterSmart data is aimed to be FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable). Open access to research data and publications is important within the context of responsible research and innovation. Ensuring research data and publications can be openly and freely accessed means that any relevant stakeholder can choose to cross-check and validate whether research data are accurately and comprehensively reported and analyzed and may also encourage re-use and re-mixing of data. A better exploitation of research data has much to offer, also in terms of alleviating the efforts required by study participants as well as researchers. Optimizing sharing of research data could potentially imply less duplication of very similar studies as previously collected data sets may be used at least as additional sources of data in new projects. Again, we emphasize that open access to research data must comply with sound research ethics (see chapter 6), ensuring not directly or indirectly identifiable information is revealed.

3.1. Data sets gathered and processed in B-WaterSmart

Within B-WaterSmart different data sets are gathered and processed by the project partners. A detailed overview of data sets was collected from WP leaders in a dedicated template at an early stage of the project. The full template used for this information collection and the results of this survey among WP leaders are included in the annex 1 to this report. The latest version of the table has been made available to all project partners on the internal project database in Nextcloud to ensure a continuous update of the data management plan. The procedure of how to update and curate these data is described in an internal document (MS05).

Within the third reporting period, a final assessment of the produced datasets (see annex 1) was made, in which all datasets were assessed regarding their confidentiality, usefulness, and reusability. The results of this assessment led to the decision that only one dataset was made publicly available via an open data repository. The dataset that was also added to EU Portal is:

- Sewer Network and Smart Water Meter Data for Modelling and Analysis of Water Distribution and Sewer Networks → <https://zenodo.org/records/14001028>

Besides, there are also some open sources codes that the B-WaterSmart Project published in open data repositories:

- Data Model Point of Interest → [GitHub - smart-data-models/dataModel.PointOfInterest: PointOfInterest Data Model](#)
- Data Model WaterQualityObserved → [dataModel.WaterQuality/WaterQualityObserved/README.md at master · smart-data-models/dataModel.WaterQuality · GitHub](#)
- Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool backend → <https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting>
- Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool frontend → <https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting-ui>

For all other data sets, it was assessed that due to confidentiality, usefulness or reusability issues, the data sets were not published separately but as part of the digital tool that they were collected for. The tool links and the persons that can be contacted in order to get access to the tools and test data sets

were included in the final and public versions of D3.4 and D3.5.

Furthermore, all public deliverables accepted by M48, were also uploaded to ZENODO, to ensure their availability after the closing of the B-WaterSmart deadline.

Deliverable No.	Deliverable Name	Zenodo Link
D1.1	CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL	https://zenodo.org/records/14011354
D1.2	First schedule of training actions and portfolio of possible contents	https://zenodo.org/records/14011490
D1.3	Recommendations for refinement of the watersmartness framework and its transformation into a dashboard-type software	https://zenodo.org/records/14011704
D2.1	Technological indicators for watersmartness	https://zenodo.org/records/14011754
D3.1	B-WaterSmart, FIWARE based interoperability framework	https://zenodo.org/records/14011177
D3.4	The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit – Final release	https://zenodo.org/records/14011771
D3.5	The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit – Final release	https://zenodo.org/records/14011819
D3.6	Water-smartness dashboard – Early release	https://zenodo.org/records/14011273

D4.1	Manual of data specifications required from mapping of actors at Living Labs	https://zenodo.org/records/14011498
D4.2	Definition of circular economy indicators for Living Labs	https://zenodo.org/records/14011384
D5.1	Manual on stakeholder mapping and engagement	https://zenodo.org/records/14011532
D5.2	Socioeconomic metrics for the water-smartness assessment framework	https://zenodo.org/records/14011725
D5.3	Preliminary report “Drivers and Barriers for Water-smart Solutions across 6 European Cases: Policy and Governance”	https://zenodo.org/records/14011430
D5.4	Preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviours towards water-smart solutions	https://zenodo.org/records/14011554
D5.5	Drivers and Barriers: Proposal for a New Governance Model	https://zenodo.org/records/14011406
D6.1	What is watersmartness and how to assess it?	https://zenodo.org/records/14011885
D6.3	Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework (V2)	https://zenodo.org/records/14011467

Table 2: Overview of the B-WaterSmart publications available on ZENODO

3.2. Making data findable

Research data collected and created within B-WaterSmart is archived at the open access European repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) to ensure re-use of public data in future research projects and follow-up studies. The Zenodo repository allows for the deposition of all kinds of digital content:

publications, data, software, multimedia etc. All published data will be provided with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI): Once published, datasets remain fixed over their lifetime, while the metadata can change.

To facilitate the upload to the open access repository Zenodo, data sets should be structured and named in accordance with the standards of the Zenodo repository from the beginning, to make data sets findable and reusable. Before uploading datasets, project partners will first have to anonymize the data sets. The responsibility for anonymizing data sets lies on the project partner uploading the data set to the repository.

Within the internal project's data repository on Nextcloud, data sets should be additionally marked in a special way of title by including a prefix "DS" for data set, followed by a living lab identification number, the partner responsible for collecting and processing the data, as well as a short title.

Confidential data will be stored, by each responsible partner, following their internal policy guidelines and providing metadata making them discoverable.

3.3. Making data openly accessible

B-WaterSmart supports open data/source/coding approaches by giving open access to at least six products. Moreover, all B-WaterSmart partners commit themselves to provide open access to any peer-reviewed scientific publications of demonstration and validation results (as far as practicable possible). Open access to publications can be ensured either by publishing in Gold open access journals or Green open access journals. To ensure high scientific quality, B-WaterSmart plans for 15 gold open access publications as part of the dissemination & communication strategy & plan. B-WaterSmart relevant journals were reviewed, and a list of relevant journals is presented in D7.5.

Gold open access means the article is available as open access by the scientific publisher. Some journals require an author-processing fee for publishing open access.

Green open access or self-archiving means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived by the researcher in an online repository (e.g., on Nextcloud or institutional repositories), in most cases after its publication. Most journals within the social sciences domains require authors to delay self-archiving to repositories to 12 months after the article first being published

Special focus of the project's dissemination activities will be given to the new open access initiative by IWA Publishing. Within this initiative, IWA Publishing has successfully transformed its journal portfolio of ten subscription title to open access from 2021 onwards and connected with libraries and institutions to subscribe to any of the journals to renew for 2021 on a Subscribe-to-Open (S2O) basis, thus contributing to making the journals free to readers and researchers worldwide.

Any peer-reviewed research publications, abstracts and presentations for international conferences are shared through the website of the project at b-watersmart.eu/. The Water Europe Marketplace (a.k.a. Knowledge Portal) developed in T7.1 and curated by Water Europe after the end of the project will be the main deposit for the data generated by the project. The data will be made available online through the WWW service. Thus, in order to discover, visualize or download the data only a common browser will be required from the user. However, before accessing some of the data, the Water Europe Marketplace will require the user to register first. For those data where the Knowledge Portal is not the preferred means for long-term storage, B-WaterSmart deposits the data (data underlying publications,

curated data and/or raw data) generated in the project, that are not protected or restricted, in the open access repository Zenodo (zenodo.org/).

For any open access publication with detailed results/information, the IPR manager will be consulted to ensure that the intended dissemination will not violate IPR interests of a B-WaterSmart partner. Original research data (in an anonymized form) will be documented and archived on Nextcloud and Zenodo and thus placed at the disposal of colleagues who want to replicate the study or elaborate on its findings.

3.4. Making data interoperable

In general, the B-WaterSmart approach (both in terms of internal design but also in terms of output and exchanged data with other systems) amounts to the usage of a few well-established interfaces where feasible; limiting the complexity generated by multiple types of interfaces (and gateways) is considered by the consortium a key-point in achieving data interoperability. Some of the various water-smart applications of the project (WP3) will be FIWARE compliant.

3.5. Increasing data re-use

B-WaterSmart will re-use publicly available data sets as far as possible instead of generating new redundant data sets (see Annex Part II). This data set will be about census population and statistical data taken from official data sets available on the websites of national statistics institutes or sectoral agencies. This information will be used to characterize the social, environmental, and economic conditions in each region involved in the project.

Increasing re-use of data sets generated by and used within the B-WaterSmart technologies and tools all project partners will ensure to make use of standard formats and apply free, libre and open-source software (FLOSS), and granting licences for open access data usage where possible. Since without a license to set out the terms of use, data is not truly open. Data without a license may be publicly accessible, but users do not have the certainty that they can use and share the data, leaving them in a legal grey area. Data licensing standards, such as the ones defined by Creative Commons, are used to lay out the openness of data sets in concrete terms, and an open data license gives explicit permission to use the data both for commercial and non-commercial purpose. According to the Open Knowledge Foundation, there are many types of licenses to choose from. The following common data licenses will be considered for use within the project:

Table 3: Examples of data licenses to be considered for use within the project

Licence	Domain	Attribution	Share-alike*	Comments
Creative Commons CCZero (CC0-1.0)	Content, Data	N	N	Dedicate to the Public Domain (all rights waived including those of attribution)
Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and Licence (PDDL-1.0)	Data	N	N	Dedicate to the Public Domain (all rights waived including those of attribution)
Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY-4.0)	Content, Data	Y	N	Credit must be given, a link to the license must be provided, changes made must be indicated. If these terms are not followed, license may be revoked
Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL-1.0)	Data	Y	Y	Credit must be given, share-alike must be assured

*Share-alike is a requirement that any materials created using the given dataset must be redistributed under the same license

Data generated through interviews and surveys will not be re-used directly due to privacy concerns (see chapter 6). To allow re-use and avoid loss of research data, different techniques could be used to disseminate its data while abiding by regulations on privacy.

One of the best ways to mitigate ethical concerns arising from the use of personal data is to anonymize them (European Commission, 2018a). "Anonymization" of data means processing it with the aim of irreversibly preventing the identification of the individual to whom it relates. Data can be considered anonymized when it does not allow identification of the individuals it is related to, and no individuals can be identified from the data by any further processing of that data or by processing it together with other information which is available or likely to be available. There are different anonymization techniques. Here are the two most relevant:

- **Generalization:** generalizing data means removing its specificity. For example, in the case of a table containing household income levels, with 4 figures mentioned: €135,000, €60,367, €89,556, and €365,784. One way of generalizing this numbers would be to write that the values are "more than €150,000, less than €80,000, between €90,000 and €120,000, and more than €300,000" respectively. Essentially it means taking exact figures, establishing a baseline category, and then obfuscating the data by assigning it to one of the categories to remove any sense of specificity from it.
- **K-anonymity;** A release of data is said to have the k-anonymity property if the information for each person contained in the release cannot be distinguished from the other individuals whose information also appear in the release. For instance, in a table composed of six attributes

(Name, Age, Gender, State of Domicile, Religion and Disease), removing the name and the religion column while generalizing the age is a way to effectively k-anonymize the data.

Anonymisation is increasingly challenging because of the potential for re-identification. Other techniques, such as “masking” or “pseudonymisation”, which are aimed solely at removing certain identifiers, may also play a role in reducing the risk of identification. However, if it is possible to re-identify the individual data subjects by reversing the pseudonymisation process, data protection obligations still apply. They cease to apply only when the data are fully and irreversibly. Pseudonyms are appropriate for qualitative data, commonly used in social sciences, such as transcripts from interviews or focus groups (European Commission, 2018a).

If personal data collected from a previous research project is intended to be used in B-WaterSmart, details regarding the initial data collection, methodology and informed consent procedure must be provided. Additionally, a declaration on having permission from the owner/manager of the dataset(s) to use the data in your project needs to be provided (European Commission, 2018a).

3.6. Handling of confidential deliverables

B-WaterSmart data is aimed to be FAIR whenever possible. However, the following deliverables are deemed to be confidential, and will only be disseminated to the members of the consortium (including the Commission Services):

Table 4: Project Deliverables that are confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination date (in month)
D1.7	Description and project planning for each LL	WP1	36 - IWW	Report	9
D2.9	Nutrient/brine separation using nitrate-selective EDR membrane and on-site production of sodium hypochlorite from RO brines	WP2	13 - AMA	Demonstrator	45
D2.10	Ammonia recovery from co-anaerobic digested sludge applying CEVAP	WP2	12 - CET	Demonstrator	45

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination date (in month)
D2.11	Vapor condensate and milk permeate treatment in dairy industry	WP2	5 - ENV	Demonstrator	45
D2.12	Combinatory treatment technologies for industrial water reuse	WP2	23 - VERI	Demonstrator	45
D2.13	Ammonia recovery from concentrated WWTP streams	WP2	23 - VERI	Demonstrator	45
D2.16	First intermediate synthesized report of technology progress and state of play across all the LLs	WP2	29 - NTNU	Report	18
D2.17	Second intermediate synthesized report of technology progress and state of play across all the LLs	WP2	29 - NTNU	Report	36
D7.1	B-WaterSmart Knowledge portal upgrades	WP7	17 - KWR	Other	12
D7.2	Long-term business plan and operation model for knowledge portal	WP7	2 - WE	Report	48

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination date (in month)
D7.7	First version exploitation and business plan for BWaterSmart solutions	WP7	35 - ADELP	Report	18
D7.8	Final exploitation and business plan for BWaterSmart solutions	WP7	35 - ADELP	Report	44
D7.9	Specific exploitation concepts for key BWaterSmart solutions	WP7	35 - ADELP	Report	48
D8.1	Project toolbox for internal communication and reporting	WP8	1 – IWW-CO	Other	1
D8.2	Scientific quality assurance plan	WP8	1 – IWW-CO	Report	3

Confidential deliverables are made available for project partners in a non-editable format (e.g. PDF) on the project's data repository on Nextcloud. The project coordinator ensures that only members of the consortium are provided with access to this data repository. Confidential deliverables and information should not be distributed to project partners via email without encryption of documents. Sharing confidential deliverables should be done via the project's internal repository only. Members of the consortium are not allowed to distribute confidential deliverables to people outside the consortium. Back-ups of the project's data repository are stored in the country of the project coordinator's institute (Germany).

To ensure confidential handling of reports but ensure their compatibility with qualitative standards of results, the quality assurance process as outlined in the Quality Assurance Plan (D8.2) was also applied to confidential deliverables. But it was ensured that only partners with a specified need to know (as outlined in the Grant Agreement) were involved in the QA process of documents.

4. Allocation of resources – Responsibility & Costs

Responsibility for maintaining this data management plan and ensuring that outputs of the project are in line with it relies on the respective thematic manager of the project, the Data and Open Access Manager at IWW.

In the B-WaterSmart project, author-publishing fees for gold open access journals have been reimbursed within the project period and budget. There are, however, a very good selection of relevant gold open access and green open access journals available that do not charge author processing fees. Scholarly publication can take a very long time, and final acceptance of all submitted manuscripts may not occur before the end of the B-WaterSmart project. For these reasons, we prioritized to submit our work to gold open access journals without author processing fees, or to green open access journals. However, as some journals charging for open access have already established agreements with some national funding institutions and universities, such options for open access with publication fees were taken into consideration when selecting journals for publication as well.

Furthermore, B-WaterSmart strives to make use of the new open access publication outlet of the European Commission: Open Research Europe. This is an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding across all subject areas. More information on Open Research Europe can be found in the project's Dissemination & communication strategy & plan (D7.5).

5. Data security – Data storage and data exchange with third countries

All raw data that is collected was and will be stored in accordance with the EU and national legislation in the country in which it is collected. The Project Coordinator IWW is subject to the laws and guidelines that are relevant for this project in Germany, which are mainly the General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679) and the Federal Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz (BDSG)). Compliance with the regulations is supervised and ensured by an external data protection commissioner (SIC GmbH).

All B-WaterSmart partners ensure that:

- Personal Data will be processed legally and fairly;
- Data will be collected for explicit and legitimate purposes and used accordingly;
- Data will be adequate, relevant, and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which it is collected and processed;
- Data will be accurate, and updated where necessary;
- Data subjects can rectify, remove, or block incorrect data about themselves;
- Data that identifies individuals (personal data) will not be kept any longer than necessary;
- We will protect personal data against accidental or lawful destruction, loss, alteration, and disclosure, particularly when processing involves data transmission over networks. Appropriate security measures will be implemented.

Ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020 will be rigorously applied, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out. The only B-WaterSmart partners that are not EU members are in Norway (Bodø municipality, SINTEF, NTNU, Krüger-Kaldnes, Techni). According to Commission decisions, personal data can flow to and from Norway without any safeguards being necessary. If technologies and tools will be tested or applied in other countries outside the European Union, the responsible partners will ensure that no data sets included in the B-WaterSmart products will be transferred without check of compliance with European legislation.

6. Ethical aspects – Handling of personal data

The concept of special categories of personal data (formerly known as “sensitive data (or)”) applies to all personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, or trade union membership (EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), article 9, 1) and requires stringent data-protection safeguards.

Ethical issues that can have an impact with regards to data sharing may derive from the collection and/or processing of personal data, required to setting up and operating the Communities of Practice and Living Labs (WP1) as well as the analysis of drivers and barriers for water-smart solutions (WP5), in order to assess the stakeholders' attitude towards water-smartness solutions, the potential acceptability of new water-smart solutions by specific end-users of water-related services (including the broader public and citizens in general) as well as the attitudes and conditions of quantitatively relevant societal groups.

The methodology used for these activities was interviews and workshops. Stakeholders were invited to participate in the project via email, so a list of contacts (name, institution, position in institution and professional email and telephone) was collected. They were asked to sign a consent form, which included detailed information about the project, what is expected from them and what kind of register of their participation (audio or video recording, photographs) will be made, as well as their right to cease participation in the project at all times. In accordance with the GDPR and national legislation, participants have the right to check the accuracy of information about themselves and to withdraw from the contact list and exercise their ARCO rights.

This research does not involve the collection and/or processing of sensitive personal data (e.g. health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, and political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction) and does not involve further processing of previously collected personal data. However, if researchers are confronted with handling sensitive personal data (due to circumstances that are not foreseeable at this point) then this may only be done, if

- the personal data was manifestly made public by the individual or
- the explicit consent of the individual was obtained (a law may rule out this option in certain cases).

The research methodologies involving human participants and personal data collection and/or processing were applied according to accepted state-of-the art standards in social sciences research, following the ethical guidelines established by the European Sociological Association and its national counterparts, as well as the recommendations in the document Ethics in Social Science and Humanities (European Commission, 2018b) and in full compliance with the regulations and procedures outlined in more detail in the following sections.

This DMP was drafted taking into account the General Data Protection Rules (GDPR) for the collection, storage and re-use of the data, in line with the following general principles. Personal data shall be:

1. processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');
2. collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the

- public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), however not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation');
3. adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
 4. accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
 5. kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject ('storage limitation');
 6. processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures ('integrity and confidentiality').

The fulfillment of the ethical requirements established in B-WaterSmart within this context were supervised by the project's ethics advisor. Specific efforts will be directed towards ensuring the privacy of participants who take part in the project studies, regardless of the country they live in. Other project partners are similarly bound by local and EU-level legislation as well as following their own in-house ethical procedures in association with research projects. We will ensure that data collection procedures comply with national and EU legislation. Once the project has finished, data will be completely anonymized, meaning links to lists of names and contact information will be deleted. Anonymised data is no longer considered personal data. If there is a significant prospect of re-identification of people whose data has been collected, the information should be treated as personal data (European Commission, 2018a). No personal data will be stored after the end of the project period.

However, the timing of the anonymization process is paramount. Anonymization of data should happen at the point and time at which the data are collected from the research subject, so that no personal data are actually processed. If anonymization takes place at a later stage, the raw data is still personal data (European Commission, 2018a).

The legal requirements for publications should not represent a risk in compromising the privacy of informants participating in the interviews, questionnaires and/or surveys within the project. Personal data is kept securely. No publications, including publications online, neither directly or indirectly will lead to a breach of agreed confidentiality and anonymity. As there will be several organizations contributing data sets, all data will be shared in a fully anonymized and de-personalized way for historical, statistical, or scientific purposes. There will not be accepted any usage of data contributed to re-identify individuals for specific marketing or profiling of users.

7. Conclusions

In this final DMP we have described the requirements imposed on B-WaterSmart about access to research data and open access to publications. Chapter 2.1, which describes the data sets, is the most important part of the DMP. This DMP acknowledges the importance of B-WaterSmart-relevant open access journals, with an emphasis on gold open access journals. For each planned publication we considered which journals are the most appropriate first choices for publication.

8. References

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ISA (2021, March 8). Code of Ethics. <https://www.isa-sociology.org/en/about-isa/code-of-ethics>.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Data production, exploitation, access, storage, and preservation during and after the project finalization

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
Technology #1: Water quantity parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g. flowrate, pressure)	Online meters, Time series, every 10 min, csv file, remote connection	Processed data	Technology provider/ owner of potable water reuse plant in beverage industry	Processed data was made available in D2.8	until M42	Processed data was made available in D2.8	Password- protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences and in scientific publications
Technology #1: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., pH, EC, turbidity)	Online sensors, Time series, every 10 min, csv file, remote connection	Processed data	Technology provider/ owner of potable water reuse plant in beverage Industry	Processed data was made available in D2.8	until M42	Processed data was made available in D2.8	Password- protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences and in scientific publications
Technology #1: Chemical and biological characterization of the treated water of the pilot (several parameters)	Sample, collection, and laboratory analysis; discrete data/Manual sampling, csv	Processed data	Technology provider/ owner of potable water reuse plant in beverage industry	Processed data was made available in D2.8	until M42	Processed data was made available in D2.8	Password- protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences and in scientific publications

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
	file, sample lab analysis							
Technology #3: Water quantity parameters (e.g., flowrate, pressure)	6 level transmitters, 10 flow transmitters, 14 pressure transmitters, 4 temperature transmitters; all: time series, every 30 sec; Wago Cloud platform			Wago Cloud platform	until M42			
Technology #3: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., pH, EC, turbidity)	5 turbidity transmitters, 5 conductivity transmitters, 2 pH transmitters, 1 redox transmitter, 1 moisture transmitter, 1 H2S sensor; all: time series, every 30 sec; Wago Cloud platform			Wago Cloud platform	until M42			

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
Technology #4: Water quantity parameters (e.g., flowrates, pressure)	excel file, time series, flowmeter measurement, pressure transmittor	All experimental data	Governance, industrial companies, scientists	CoP and industrial meetings	Until M42	Meetings material, requests with specific focus, peer-reviewed publications	Not applicable	Congress, CoP and industrial meetings, peer- reviewed publications
Technology #4: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., EC)	excel file, time series, conductivity sensor	All experimental data	Governance, industrial companies, scientists	CoP and industrial meetings	Until M42	Meetings material, requests with specific focus, peer-reviewed publications	Not applicable	Congress, CoP and industrial meetings, peer- reviewed publications
Technology #5: Water quantity parameters (e.g., flowrates, pressure, temperature)	5 level transmitters, 5 flow transmitters, 11 pressure transmitters, 3 temperatures transmitters: time series			Wago Cloud platform (partly)				
Technology #5: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., turbidity, Temperature,	3 turbidity transmitters, 1 moisture transmittor, 1 H2S sensor, 3 conductivity transmitters, 1 pH/T/ORP			Wago Cloud platform (partly)				

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
moisture, H2S, pH)	transmitters, time series							
Technology #6: Water quantity parameters (e.g., Physical water parameters,)	time series/ calculation on demand, time series, automated calculation/man ual recording	private	Technology provider/ owner of water reuse plant in dairy Industry/ approving authorities	Datasets are made accessible for the responsible consortium partners (ENV, IWW, OOWV, DMK) by the digital service platform "WaterExpert" of ENV. Extracts of datasets are shared within the consortium by presentations and deliverables. Extracts of datasets will be shared with approving authorities, in order to apply for a permit to reuse cow water.	until M43	"Water Expert" cloud platform: Download of datasets as PDF-, Excel- or CSV-files dd	All the data is stored in a cloud and backed up there. Raw data cannot be changed, only its visualisation and calculation.	Extracts of datasets are available to public in presentations and other publications.

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
Technology #6: Water quality parameters in several locations of the pilot (e.g., Microbiological cultural parameter, Cell counts non- culturable, Bacterial regrowth potential, cell counts non- culturable online, Inorganic Ions, Trace substances)	manual readings for different sampling rounds; laboratory analysis/flow cytometer/Bacto Sense/on site, on demand/online measurements/r emote by processing of online data	Private	Technology provider/ owner of water reuse plant in dairy Industry/ approving authorities	Datasets are only accessible by contacting the responsible consortium partners. Extracts of datasets are shared within the consortium by presentations and deliverables. Extracts of datasets will be shared with approving authorities, in order to apply for a permit to reuse cow water.	until M43	Excel-/ CSV-/ NCF- files, PDF documents,	company own servers of the responsible partners (ENV, IWW, OOWV, DMK)	Extracts of datasets are available to public in presentations and other publications.
Technology #7: Water quantity parameters (e.g., flows, pressure, temperature)	5 flowmeters; Time series, every 30 sec; USB extraction/Remo te connection	None	Water utility	Through a shared drive repository with the water utility, by tech owner (CET)	until M48	Excel files and reports (word and powerpoint documents)	Own google drive repository	In local, national and international technical conferences and events In internal and external meetings with stakeholders

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
Technology #7: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., conductivity, Concentration of major cations/anions/t urbidity, chemical oxygen demand, pH)	6 conductivity meters, sample collection and laboratory analysis etc.; Manual sampling, several samples per batch; Sample lab analysis	None	Water utility	Through a shared drive repository with the water utility, by tech owner (CET)	until M48	Excel files and reports (word and powerpoint documents)	Own google drive repository	In local, national and international technical conferences and events In internal and external meetings with stakeholders
Technology #9: conductivity	conductivity meter; time series, every 30 sec	None	Water utility	Through a shared drive repository with the water utility, by tech owner (CET)	until M48	Excel files and reports (word and powerpoint documents)	Own google drive repository	In local, national and international technical conferences and events In internal and external meetings with stakeholders
Technology #10: Water quantity parameters (e.g., flow, temperature,	2 temperature transmitter, 1 gas flow meter, 1 pressure transmitter, Time series, every 30 sec/Manual	None	Water utility	Through a shared drive repository with the water utility, by tech owner (CET)	until M42	Excel files and reports (word and powerpoint documents)	Own google drive repository	In local, national and international technical conferences and events In internal and external

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
sludge level, pressure)	reading, 1 time per day							meetings with stakeholders
Technology #10: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., CO ₂ , methane, pH, conductivity, COD, TS, VS, total nitrogen, total phosphorus)	1 Methane detector, Sample collection and laboratory analysis; Manual sampling, 2 samples per week	None	Water utility	Through a shared drive repository with the water utility, by tech owner (CET)	until M42	Excel files and reports (word and powerpoint documents)	Own google drive repository	In local, national and international technical conferences and events In internal and external meetings with stakeholders
Technology #11: Water quantity parameters (e.g., temperature, flow)	Time series	All experimental data	Utilities, governance, scientists	CoP meetings, using online DSS (#19), peer-reviewed publications	Until M46	Meetings material, requests with specific focus, peer-reviewed publications	Not applicable	Congress, CoP and industrial meetings, peer-reviewed publications
Technology #11: Water quality parameters in several locations the pilot (e.g., pH, analytic data of pollutants and	Continuous automatic in-field measurement/m annual sampling	All experimental data	Utilities, governance, scientists	CoP meetings, using online DSS (#19), peer-reviewed publications	Until M46	Meetings material, requests with specific focus, peer-reviewed publications	Not applicable	Congress, CoP and industrial meetings, peer-reviewed publications

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
process parameters)								
Tool #14: Wastewater flow	2 flow meters, 5 min resolution, total length 1,5 year	OA	Wastewater network operator, planner and research	Throughout the project, between task members, classified, dynamic data: https://nordkont.akt.developer.azure-api.net/	Until M48	Publicly: Zenodo.org	Password- protected computers, password protected documents, computer securely stored when not in use	Anonymized data, open access: https://zenodo.org/records/14001028
Tool #15: Water flow	27 smart water meter, time series, SWMs were in use between September 2023 - June 2024 (9 months), 1 month of data shared for open access (for the water leakage simulation performed in September 2023)	Partly OA	Water network operator and research for leakage detection algorithms	Throughout the project, between task members, classified dynamic data: https://nordkont.akt.developer.azure-api.net/ Throughout the project, between task members, classified, static data: Onedrive with two factor authentication with private sharing, excel	Until M48	Publicly: Zenodo.org	Password- protected computers, password protected documents, computer securely stored when not in use	Anonymized data, open access: https://zenodo.org/records/14001028

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
				and word files with password protection.				
Tool #20: Water consumption, wastewater treated	Time series, annual							
Tool #20: Chemical characterization of the treated water (residual chlorine, ammonia)	Sample collection and laboratory analysis							
Tool #24: Chemical characterization of the treated water (residual chlorine, ammonia)	Sample collection and laboratory analysis	Processed data	Distribution network manager	Technical staff	Until M48	Processed data was made available in OA publications	Password- protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences and in scientific publications
Tool #24: Wastewater flow velocity in the distribution network (range)	Flow velocity calculated by data processing of an online flowmeter set- up in	Processed data	Distribution network manager	Technical staff	Until M48	Processed data was made available in OA publications	Password- protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
	measurement campaigns							and in scientific publications
Tool #25: Water/phosphorus demand, groundwater/spring water, reclaimed water/drinkwater available	Flow meter, Sample collection and laboratory analysis; Time series, monthly	Processed data	Municipal decision maker and practitioners	Technical staff	During all the project	Processed data will be made available in OA publications	Password-protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences and in scientific publications
Tool #27: Water reuse system configuration	Predefined list (groups): hazards, exposure routes, exposure sites, activities, population at risk, environment at risk	Processed data	Green area designer and manager	Technical staff	During all the project	Processed data was made available in an OA publication	Password-protected computers	Processed data was and will be presented in conferences and in scientific publications
Tool #28: water consumption data	Flow meter; time series in 15-minute time steps	none	Researchers on water demand and water use (household/ neighbourhood level)	Sensitive data: data classified as confidential; data sharing only with explicit permission of OOWV. Please see contact in D3.5.	At least until M48	Documented in D3.5 (https://zenodo.org/records/14011819) and in a confidential report	Data owner internal data management system	-

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
Tool #28: water consumption data	Flow meter; time series in 15-minute time steps	OA	Researchers on water demand and water use (household/ neighbourhood level)	https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting .	M24	Documented in D3.5 (https://zenodo.org/records/14011819) and https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting .	Github version management	https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting
Tool #33: Alternative water supply system; water distribution and building infrastructure, Irrigation system, green roof and facades and pavement, swimming pool, fixtures, devices, etc.	Evidence based certification; data is collected through building assessment	Data is classified as OA to building owners	Municipalities for resilience planning and investment. Policymakers to guide climate strategy, funding and reporting	climatecertificat es.adene.pt platform	Until M48	Trough a certificate with the results of the assesments.	ADENE servers	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)
Water balance (input-output) – urban water cycle or industrial water processes-	Data collected from Living Lab owners, mentors and technology developers	Only results of data processing	Technology developers, Water utilities, Scientific community	Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D4.3. Data sets collected during	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
				interviews and questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud				Project deliverables (reports)
Reclaimed water uses for non-potable (irrigation, cleaning, industrial, etc.)	Data collected from Living Lab owners, mentors and technology developers	Only results of data processing	Technology developers, Water utilities, Scientific community	Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D4.3. Data sets collected during interviews and questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)
Energy balance (energy consumption)	Data collected from Living Lab owners, mentors and	Only results of data processing	Technology developers, Water utilities,	Only results of data processing will be published as open access	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
and energy generation)	technology developers		Scientific community	by means of D4.3. Data sets collected during interviews and questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud				Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)
Waste production (type of wastes) and waste treatment destinations (landfill, incineration, etc.)	Data collected from Living Lab owners, mentors and technology developers	Only results of data processing	Technology developers, Water utilities, Scientific community	Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D4.3. Data sets collected during interviews and questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
Regulators barriers (water, energy, waste)	Living lab stakeholders interviews, CoP participants interviews	Only results of data processing	Technology developers, Water utilities, Scientific community	Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D4.3. Data sets collected during interviews and questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)
Costs of water management, cost of energy acquisition/prod uction, waste, cost of waste treatments	Literature review	private	Technology developers, Water utilities, Scientific community	Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D4.3. Data sets collected during interviews and questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
				storage and sharing platform NextCloud.				
Current business models	Assessment which Departments of Finance	private	Business models could be interesting as an offer-demand market between the stakeholder in each LL	Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D4.4. Data collected during assessments are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud.	During all the project	Excel files and reports (pdf)	Nextcloud and own shared drive (CET)	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)
Social barriers and drivers to water-smart solutions (e.g., water reuse); opinions and perceptions on water issues (climate change, scarcity,	Focus groups and workshops (recorded and transcribed)	Pseudonymised transcripts	Academic researchers Doctoral students Policy analysts		M6-36	Pdf documents stored in Nextcloud; Reports based on CoPs workshops (D5.4; D5.7)	Password- protected computers, securely stored when not in use Project repository on Nextcloud	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
overlapping demands)								
Assessment of stakeholder's attitudes: perceptions and acceptability of the solutions proposed by B- WaterSmart	Surveys applied to CoPs members	Anonymised and aggregated Excel data sets	Academic researchers Doctoral students		M10-M48	Reports based on CoPs workshops (D5.7)	Password- protected computers, securely stored when not in use Project repository on Nextcloud	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports)
Policy-related barriers and drivers to water- smart solutions (e.g., water reuse)	Content analysis of policy documents (legislation, regulations, strategies, and plans – international, EU, national, regional, local)	No sensitive data, all data can be open access	Academic researchers Doctoral students Policy analysts Policymakers (e.g., government institutions)		M10-M42	Pdf documents stored on Nextcloud	Password- protected computers, securely stored when not in use Project repository on Nextcloud	CoPs activities Academic conferences Academic publications (articles) Project website Project deliverables (reports) Policy briefs

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
<p>General, technical, and commercial description of B-WaterSmart products (Technologies and Data Applications) necessary to identify exploitable results and to develop specific exploitation routes</p>	<p>Desk research, online questionnaires, interviews with solution providers and assessments of pilot plants through site visits of LLs</p>	<p>Only results of data processing to which the respective person has given her/his consent will be published as open access by means of D7.7 and D7.8.</p>	<p>B-WaterSmart solution providers to exploit and transfer/adapt their products across Europe and beyond.</p> <p>End-users interested in water smart technologies and data applications.</p> <p>Investors and implementers including municipalities, governments, development banks, funding agencies, private investors interested in water smart innovations and in fostering a circular and water smart economy.</p>	<p>Only results of data processing will be published as open access by means of D7.7 and D7.8.</p> <p>Data sets collected during interviews and online questionnaires are only made accessible within the entire consortium through the data storage and sharing platform NextCloud.</p>	<p>Data collection will be updated regularly during the entire project lifespan</p>	<p>Data sets collected during interviews, online questionnaires and site visits will be documented and structured accessible for project partners on NextCloud.</p>	<p>adelphi company own server</p>	<p>Through D7.7 and D7.8 on the B-WaterSmart Website and further social media channels (e.g., adelphi Website, Facebook, Twitter)</p>

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
			Regulators dealing with water issues. Further beneficiaries of water smart innovations					
Data necessary to identify application potential of specific sites in Europe and beyond: data on the environmental and geographical conditions, institutional set up, legal framework, market conditions etc.	Desk research, online questionnaires, interviews with stakeholders and site visits/workshops and public events; Only data that is openly accessible or has been released as such by the owner is collected.	Same as cell above	Same as cell above	Same as cell above	Same as cell above	Data sets collected during interviews, online questionnaires, site visits, workshops and public events will be documented and structured accessible for project partners on NextCloud.	Same as cell above	Same as cell above
Personal data of B-WaterSmart solution providers and CoPs	Desk research, online questionnaires, interviews with solution providers	All personal data will be protected from access by unauthorised parties and from unauthorised	-	-	Same as cell above	-	Same as cell above	-

Type of data/ data description	Methodology of data production	Which data sets are classified as Open Access	To whom data could be useful	How data will be shared / by whom and where	When was data produced	Data documentation and how that will be made available	How is proper backup and versioning realised?	How the data will be disseminated
		disclosure. Personal data will not be supplied to third parties without authorisation.						

Annex 2- Data sets that are reused within the project

Type of data	Format of data	Source
Tool #29: Leakage data	Time series	https://zenodo.org/records/4017659
Tool #33: Climate risk maps	Visual, images	https://www.wri.org/aqueduct
Tool #33: Hydrologic resources portal	Time series	https://snirh.apambiente.pt/index.php?idMain=1&idItem=1.3&salbufeirasimbolo=16H/01A

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